

MODEL BASED PROCESSING OF HYBRID RTM PARTS

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ABSTRACT

This paper provides a guideline for the online application of phenomenological models to improve the quality of hybrid parts manufactured by the resin transfer moulding (RTM) process. A main aspect is to show how the required input data can be generated and how the models can be implemented into the RTM process. For this purpose, the paper discusses the processing steps resin injection and curing.

1 INTRODUCTION

The RTM process is well known in the composite industry and can be used to produce net-shape, high quality structural parts [1]. A modification of this process is the so called One-Shot-Hybrid (OSH)-RTM process [2,3]. It is able to produce multi-material hybrid parts in a single process. There, the injected resin system acts as polymer matrix for the composite as well as an adhesive towards the non-composite materials in the hybrid setup. This single-step processing approach reduces production time and costs.

The OSH-RTM process can be divided into six steps:

- Cutting of the textile
- Preforming
- Placing of the preform and metal inside the mould and closing of the mould
- Resin injection
- Curing
- Opening of the mould and demoulding of the part

Nevertheless, the process still hides challenges regarding void content and defined curing degree of the final parts. Especially the void content needs to be mentioned as it does not only affects the mechanical properties [4–6] of the composite component but can also reduce the interface area towards the non-composite constituents when migrating towards the surface of the composite.

In the past, a lot of effort was put into the development of control systems for composite processes [7–9]. While most of them did only focus on the modelling and simulation of the process [10–14] other did also prove their concepts by experiments [15–18].

It was proven, that there is an ideal flow front velocity which is producing a minimum amount of voids inside the composite structure [19–21]. The void formation is linked to two flow contributions: the capillary flow on the one hand and the flow induced by the injection unit. The least voids are produced if both flow velocities are the same. Various methods shown how the ideal velocity can be determined [22–24]. However, mechanisms such as preform compaction in the mould or void transport during flushing are neglected in parts of these studies.

Especially the preform compaction, which is resulting in a compaction pressure while the mould is closed, needs to be considered [25,26]. It does not only effect the porosity and permeability of the preform but also is influenced during the injection stage as a result of lubrication effects due to the wetting of the fibres [27]. This is important, as surface flat mould mounted pressure transducers can only measure the sum of compaction pressure and hydraulic pressure created by the injected matrix system.

Besides the void content, the curing degree of the resin system has the biggest influence onto the mechanical properties of the composite. To evaluate the crosslinking reaction of an epoxy resin the dynamic scanning calorimetry (DSC) can be used. It measures the heat flow, which is directly linked to the conversion rate of the resin. Furthermore it can be used to evaluate the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the thermoset [28–30]. However, this measurement can only be made outside of the mould. Some recent research also showed some interesting results by utilizing NIR spectroscopy, but maturation level is low and further research is necessary [31,32]. To measure the conversion rate inside the mould a direct current (DC) sensor can be used [33]. The sensor measures the surface resistivity of the composite while curing. Due to a change of ion-mobility, the resistance is raising with a higher degree of cure [34]. At curing degrees beyond the gelation point the viscosity is directly linked to the measured resistance. Due to the gelation theory by Flory, the degree of cure can be calculated at this point by knowing the amount of reactive groups of the resin and hardener [35]. After this point a direct correlation of the resistivity with the glass transition temperature is supposed [36]. However, DC sensor measurements showed large deviations regarding the start and end values of the measured data in a historic study [37]. To overcome this issue, which might be linked to the amount of release agent or dirt on the sensing surface, a self-learning algorithm predicting the T_g was supposed [38]. Neural network approaches are interesting, nevertheless they have drawbacks as they need large amounts of training data. This work will show an approach in evaluating the T_g by applying curve fitting techniques which can be applied to online sensor data.

2 OPERATING PRINCIPLE

2.1 Flow front velocity control

Darcy's law is the fundamental correlation behind this model-based processing approach [39]. Darcy flow velocity v_d can be calculated by Equation (1),

$$v_d = -\frac{1}{\mu} K \nabla p, \quad (1)$$

where μ is the viscosity of the resin system and K is the permeability of the preform. These two values need to be measured previous to the processing, while the pressure gradient ∇p needs to be measured and controlled during the resin injection stage. To reduce the void content the ideal flow front velocity v_f must be characterized in advance while the link between v_d and v_f is the porosity \emptyset of the preform. Equation (2) shows the correlation:

$$v_f = \frac{v_d}{\emptyset}. \quad (2)$$

Figure 1: Operating principle of the flow speed controller.

To use the shown correlation within a control system, a flow speed controller (FSC) was developed. The principle of the controller is shown in Fig. 1. It also shows Darcy's law in the 1D form. In this case, the pressure gradient can be evaluated easily by the use of two pressure sensors, which are placed inside the mould in a defined distance. As soon as the flow front reaches the second sensor, the control mode switches from a defined mass flow towards the defined ideal flow velocity. It has to be noted, that this simplified form can only be applied to components which are filled by mainly 1D flow due to their geometry.

In order to ensure fast reaction time, the controller is located on a real-time-capable PLC with connected I/O modules. The I/O modules collect the sensor data, while the PLCs controls the mass flow to ensure the ideal flow velocity inside the mould. The calculated mass flow acts as a set point for the Tartler (Germany) Nodopur VS- 2K injection unit.

2.2 Cure monitoring

As mentioned above [34], the viscosity of the resin and the measured resistivity are showing a direct correlation which can be described by Equation (3):

$$\sigma \cdot \mu^k = \text{const.} = C. \quad (3)$$

Therefore, the resistance σ can be used to predict the viscosity μ by evaluating the constants k and C . This leads to:

$$\sigma = \frac{C}{\mu^k}. \quad (4)$$

After the gelation point, this relation does not fit anymore. Related to Flory theory [35], the curing degree at the gelation time is always the same and can be calculated according to Equation (5):

$$\alpha_g = \left(\frac{1}{(f_a - 1)(f_e - 1)} \right)^{1/2}. \quad (5)$$

There, the degree of cure at the gelation point α_g is linked to the amount of chemically reactive groups of the resin (f_a) and the curing agent (f_e). By the use of isothermal DSC measurements with different curing times and therefore different curing degrees the DiBenedetto equation [40] can be used to derive a T_g along the curing degree α . Equation (6) shows the DiBenedetto equation in a special form:

$$T_g(\alpha) = T_{g0} + \frac{\lambda \cdot \alpha(T_{g\infty} - T_{g0})}{1 - (1 - \lambda)\alpha}. \quad (6)$$

Therein, T_{g0} is the T_g of the uncured resin and $T_{g\infty}$ is the maximum reachable T_g of the resin system. λ is a fitting parameter used to fit the model to the measured data. By applying a time dependent curing degree from an isothermal DSC measurement to the model, which is related to the curing conditions in the RTM mould, a time dependent T_g can be achieved. As a linear correlation between the logarithm of the resistance σ and T_g is supposed, Equation (7) needs to be fulfilled:

$$T_g(\sigma) = p_1 \cdot \log(\sigma) + p_2. \quad (7)$$

In this case, p_1 and p_2 are fitting parameters.

3 EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 Ideal flow front velocity

The ideal flow front velocity is strongly dependent on the used fabric and fibre volume fraction on the one hand and the used matrix system and its temperature on the other hand. Therefore, the capillary flow velocity needs to be characterized under real processing conditions. A capillary flow front rise test rig which is using preforms in the dimension of 50 x 60 mm was used [41]. The preform consisting of 6 layers (EBX800 glass fibre fabric with an aerial weight of 801 g/m² from Saati (Italy)) was clamped into the sample holder with a 4 mm cavity frame. This results in a fibre volume fraction of 47.43%. The

layers of the biaxial non crimped fabric (NCF) were cut in a 45° angle to provide a $0/90^\circ$ fibre orientation in the preform. To achieve a symmetric layup 3 of the layers were mirrored. The whole sample holder with the preform as well as the two components of the epoxy resin (Epinal IR 77.55-A1 and Epinal IH 77.55-B1, provided by bto-epoxy (Austria)) were heated up to 70°C in an oven. Right before the capillary flow experiment was started, the epoxy resin system was mixed at a mixing ratio of 100:32. Figure 2 shows the setup of the capillary flow velocity measurement.

Figure 2: Capillary flow velocity measurement.

In order to evaluate the ideal flow front velocity, the velocity of the flow front at the lowest contact point needs to be evaluated. As the velocity at time zero is forced to be zero, only an extrapolation to this point can reveal the velocity at this point. The extrapolation of the mean of five measurements in Fig. 3 reveals an ideal flow front velocity of 5.2 ± 1.2 mm/s which corresponds to a Darcy velocity of approximately 2.7 mm/s.

Figure 3: Capillary flow velocity over height.

3.2 Resin Viscosity

In order to evaluate the dynamic resin viscosity, the same procedure for preheating the two components as described before was used. The measurements were carried out with an Anton Paar MCR501 (Austria) rheometer with a heated hood at 70°C . After mixing the components the resin system was filled in the measuring cup and measured with a D-PP25-SN0 measuring system at a gap size of 1 mm with a shear rate of 10 s^{-1} . Figure 4 shows the mean of three viscosity measurements of the resin system up to 100 s.

Figure 4: Resin viscosity over time at 70°C.

As the dynamic viscosity in this time period is only varying in the range of 126 - 139 mPa s it can be assumed as constant for the period of the filling phase of the composite part as well as for the capillary experiments. The mean value was found at 130 ± 4 mPa s.

3.3 Preform Permeability

One of the most important parameter in Darcy's law is the permeability. To characterize the 2D plane permeability tensor, in-plane permeability experiments following the radial flow principle were carried out [42–44]. In order to reach similar boundary conditions, the preform and cavity height was the same as in the following RTM experiment. As injected fluid a coloured sunflower oil was used. Figure 5 shows the advancing flow front which was used to measure the permeabilities along the main axis of the ellipsoid as well as the orientation angle towards the main axis.

Figure 5: Flow front development during the permeability measurement.

The average major and minor in-plane permeability values K_1 and K_2 , determined from 5 experiments at repeatable conditions were found at $1.26 \pm 0.10 \text{ E-}10 \text{ m}^2$ and $0.85 \pm 0.08 \text{ E-}10 \text{ m}^2$, respectively. The orientation angle of the major principled flow direction was found as $21.4 \pm 8.8^\circ$. In order to calculate the permeability in the flow direction the permeability tensor needs to be rotated which results in a permeability k_y of $1.17 \text{ E-}10 \text{ m}^2$ along the y-axis.

3.4 Resin Curing

In order to reduce the curing time for the DC and DSC measurements, the experiments were carried out at 100°C. Regarding to the manufacturer the proposed curing cycle for this material is 25 min at 100°C. The resin viscosity was measured with the same setup as described before by only changing the temperature to 100°C.

In order to determine the fitting parameter λ of the DiBenedetto equation, DSC measurements were carried out. T_{g0} was measured to be -21.3°C and $T_{g\infty}$ 132°C (300 min at 100°C) respectively. Further T_g measurement points were added at a curing degree of 90% (25 min at 100°C) resulting in a λ of 0.3199.

Furthermore, the heat flow of the measurement with a duration of 300 min was used to evaluate the curing degree over time.

The DC sensor was mounted in the plate mould near the injection gate. The mould was heated to 100°C and the data of the resistance measurement was evaluated as soon as the injection was stopped.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Flow speed control

The described material characterization leads to the 1D Darcy's law in the form shown in Equation (6). As all other parameters are defined only Δp remains controllable.

$$2.7 \cdot 10^{-3} = - \frac{1.17 \times 10^{-10}}{0.13} \cdot \frac{\Delta p}{0.125} \quad (6)$$

The pressure difference Δp can directly be influenced by the mass flow and therefore is controllable by the injection unit. The concept was proven in a production related environment using a mold with a cavity measuring $270 \times 270 \times 4$ mm. The mold was tempered at 70°C and placed in a Langzauner (Austria) LZT-OK-80-SO press applying a force of 360 kN while closed. The mixing head of the injection unit was directly connected with the line distributor of the mould by the use of a Tartler Flowstop system.

The two pressure sensors were put along the centre line of the resin flow path. One sensor is located at a flow path length of 10 mm while the second sensor was located at 135 mm.

Figure 6 illustrates the function of the FSC. The signals of the pressure sensors p_1 and p_2 were used to calculate the flow speed. The FSC starts to control the flow speed after p_2 is reached (at about 30 s in the case shown in the Figure 6). Until this point the flow front propagates through the preform and therefore the calculated flow speed does not provide real values.

Figure 6: Measured and controlled flow speed with regarding pressure data of the pressure sensors p_1 and p_2 in the flat plate tool at 70°C.

However, after 30 s the flow speed is controlled at the required level. For such simple moulds as the used plate mould the shown strategy can also be used to detect race tracking. This can be done by

comparing the measured flow speed with the mass flow rate provided by the injection unit. As volume constancy can be presumed the mass flow rate needs to be divided by the density of the resin system and the cross-section of the mould to get the mean flow speed along the cross-section. If the calculated value is much higher than the measured Darcy flow speed, race tracking can be expected.

Figure 7: Results of the evaluation of the gelation time (t_g) and the glass transition temperature (T_g) by the use of DC measurements and pointwise curve fitting.

4.2 Resin Curing

In order to evaluate the gelation time while curing, the viscosity curve, the resistivity measurement and the correlation shown in Equation (4) were used (Figure 7). After reaching 20 measurement points (equal to 20 s) of the DC sensor a nonlinear least squares algorithm was used to evaluate the parameters k and C of Equation (4). The fitting algorithm was now applied for each dataset when the DC sensor provided a new data point. The first diagram in the “Evaluation of gelation time” column shows the goodness of fit (GoF) evolution provided by this technique. At some point, the GoF is starting to decrease after reaching a maximum. This is the point where the model relation proposed in Equation (3)

can't be applied anymore. Therefore, this point was defined to be the gelation time (t_g). Comparing the evaluation of five measurements resulting in a t_g of 357 ± 30 s with the results from rheological measurements resulting in 364 s shows a good match. Due to Flory theory, the degree of cure can be calculated at this point. Regarding the formulation of the resin system α_g is 57.7% at this time. The knowledge of the curing degree and the correlation between T_g and σ can now be used to model the change of T_g with respect to time. For this case a linear least squares fitting algorithm is sufficient. The procedure was carried out similar to the one described before, starting at t_g . The fit shows a good linear correlation to the time dependent T_g evaluated by the DiBenedetto equation with the time dependent degree of cure evaluated by the DSC measurement. This can be seen in the first two graphs in the "Evaluation of T_g " column in Figure 7. However, at some point the GoF drops continually. The last peak before this happens was defined as onset of vitrification. At this point the T_g is getting close to the curing temperature, which results in a reduction of mobility of the molecules and therefore a reduction in change of cure. This also effects the resistivity measurement. Here, new fitting parameters need to be found. The derived model was again achieved by linear fitting of the parameters in Equation (7).

5 CONCLUSIONS

The work presented in this paper shows a strategy how to generate input data for phenomenological models, which are able to optimize the OSH-RTM process. The experimental procedures to gain the needed model parameters as well as the application of the models in the real process environment were shown.

Two strategies, which can improve the quality of the produced components using sensor data to control and evaluate the RTM process while the mould is closed are presented. The application of the ideal flow velocity points towards the reduction of the void content in the final part. The use of production related equipment (injection unit, press, mould) shows that such an approach can also be transferred to industry. The application of a controlled filling velocity does not only reduce the void content, but also leads to a constant material quality along the flow path of the component.

The second strategy points to a constant T_g of the produced components. This guarantees constant quality of the temperature dependent behaviour of the parts. The shown strategy is applicable to the process without using a self-learning algorithm and only a small amount of preliminary measurements needs to be carried out. The shown algorithm is able to detect the gelation point as well as the onset of vitrification. Nevertheless, it must be stated, that the time deviation of the evaluated t_g is quite high. This can be linked to inaccurate mixing behaviour of the injection unit or unequal contact of the fibre textile with the sensor surface at the different experiments. In the end of the curing stage the model underestimates the T_g to a small amount. This might lead to slightly higher curing times as needed. However, the needed T_g will be reached and the produced parts will meet the quality criteria.

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